

3-HYDROXY-1-*p*-SULPHONATOPHENYL-3-PHENYLTRIAZINE AS AN INDIRECT SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC REAGENT FOR FLUORIDE

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The fading of ferric-3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine, a bluish black complex with fluoride ions, is made the basis for the indirect spectrophotometric determination of fluoride in the concentration range of 0.5 to 40 p.p.m. Phosphate, borate, citrate, tartrate, oxalate, and cyanide interfere; other common anions do not. This method can be applied for determining fluoride in water samples.

Fluoride determinations have become increasingly important in recent years, and several spectrophotometric methods are described in the literature. As fluoride does not form coloured complexes, only indirect spectrophotometric methods have been proposed to date. These procedures are based on measuring the bleaching of some coloured metal complex by the formation of stable complex between the metal ion and fluoride.

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine develops an intense bluish black, water-soluble colour with Fe(III) (Gupta and Sogani, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 97). In the present investigation the fading of this colour with fluoride ions is made the basis for the indirect spectrophotometric determination of fluoride in micro quantities. The fading is directly proportional to the amount of ferric ions withdrawn from the system in the formation of more stable ferric fluoride complex. The following equilibria exist :

The extent to which the reaction proceeds depends on the relative stabilities of FeR_3 and $[\text{FeF}_6]^{3-}$ complexes in the reaction mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard Sodium Fluoride Solution.—Pure sodium fluoride (5.0 g.) was dissolved in distilled water and the volume made to 500 c.c. Fluoride content was determined gravimetrically by cad chlorofluoride method (Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 1939, p. 405) and was diluted so as to contain 80 p.p.m. of fluoride.

Standard ferric chloride, reagent and buffer solutions, and instruments were the same as described earlier (*loc. cit.*).

Calibration Curve.—In a volume of 50 c.c., 10 c.c. of the standard ferric chloride solution ($M \times 10^{-3}$) was found to produce a colour, readable by the photoelectric colorimeter. Required amounts of 10% HCl (v/v) and 10% sodium acetate (w/v) solution were added so as to bring the pH to ~ 3.0 after necessary dilution. It was followed by 10 c.c. of 0.4% aqueous reagent

solution. Different volumes of the standard fluoride solution were added in a series of solutions, prepared as described above. The volume was then made up to the mark and absorbance was measured at 650 m μ , taking water in the reference cell.

Fig. 1 shows the effect of increasing fluoride concentration on fading of bluish black iron complex.

FIG. 1

The amount of iron withdrawn from reaction is proportional to the concentration of fluoride in the range from 0.5 to 40 p.p.m. of fluoride. After 40 p.p.m. of fluoride the fading of colour is less than the amount of fluoride added. Ions forming stable complexes with Fe(III) like phosphate, oxalate, citrate, tartrate, cyanide, etc., or with fluoride ion, like borate, interfere; common anions like chloride, sulphate, nitrate, acetate, etc. do not interfere in the determination.

Effect of Time.—An experiment was performed to find out the time taken for the establishment of the equilibrium in the reaction (ii). A sample was prepared as described above and the absorbance measured at different intervals of time. There was no change in the absorbance with time. Hence the equilibrium is established almost instantaneously.

Determination of Fluoride in Water.—Boruff and Abbott have reported (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1933, 5, 236) that water containing small quantities of fluorides, when made alkaline to phenolphthalein or litmus, can be concentrated without loss of fluorine. Most natural waters do not contain enough phosphate or borate in the volume used for determination of fluoride to interfere with the accuracy of the method.

A 100 c.c. sample of water was taken in a shallow beaker, made alkaline to phenolphthalein, and concentrated to 25 to 30 c.c. by gentle heating. The quantity of the sample to be taken depends upon the fluoride content present, which should be within 0.025 to 2 mg. After cooling, the pH was adjusted to about 3.0 by adding 10% HCl (v/v). In a 50 c.c. volumetric flask standard ferric chloride, buffer solutions, and reagent solution were added, as described earlier, followed by the sample of water prepared, as described above. After making up the volume to the mark, the absorbance was measured at 650 m μ , taking water as a reference solution. The amount of fluoride was read from the calibration curve.

DISCUSSION

Fluoride is determined by its fading action on the colour of ferric thiocyanate (Foster, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1933, 5, 234), acetylacetone (Armstrong, *ibid.*, p. 300), 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (Fahey, *ibid.*, 1939, 11, 362), sulphosalicylic acid (Monnier *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, 29, 521), and salicylic acid (Kortum and Seller, *Angew. Chem.*, 1947, A 59, 159). The complexes of zirconium and thorium with hydroxyanthraquinones have been successfully used (Bumstead and Wells, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 1595; Talvite, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal.*

Ed., 1943, 15, 620; Normik, *Acta Polytech., Chem. Met. Ser.*, 1953, 3, vii, 121). The decoloration of aluminium—chromeazurol (McNulty and Woolard, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 13, 134) and eriochromecyanine (McNulty *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, 14, 368) complexes by fluoride have been studied. A comparative study of some of the important methods has been made by Kojima *et al.* (*Japan Analyst*, 1955, 4, 607).

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine introduces one more compound in the list of good reagents for the indirect spectrophotometric determination of fluoride. No claim for its superiority over other reagents is made.

The authors express their gratitude to Principal Bhim Sen for providing facilities in the college.

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Received May 12, 1960.